

EXPRESSION OF CONCERN (EoC)

Date: Friday, 3 April 2026

Subject: Formal Warning and Expression of Concern regarding Published Article

Status: Retraction Request Pending (No response from Publisher for 1 months)

1. Original Article Information

- **Title:** Tatalaksana Anestesi Pada Pasien Dengan Severe Aortic Stenosis Dengan Tindakan Hemicolecotomy Dextra
- **Authors:** Diah Virayanti; Otniel Adrians Labobar; Christopher Ryalino; Tjokorda Gde Agung Senapathi
- **Journal:** Syntax Literate: Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia
- **Volume/Issue/Pages:** Vol. 10 No. 1 (2025): Syntax Literate: Jurnal Ilmiah Indonesia
- **DOI:** <https://doi.org/10.36418/syntax-literate.v10i1.56469>
- **Publication Date:** 2025-02-11

2. Nature of Concern

The corresponding author(s) hereby issue this Expression of Concern to notify the academic community and potential readers regarding the validity of the findings in the aforementioned article.

After a thorough post-publication review, we have identified:

- **Ethical Problems** that fundamentally unethical, and affects the core conclusions of the study.

3. Current Status and Recommendation

A formal request for **Retraction** was submitted to the editorial office of *Syntax Literate* on **Friday, 13 March 2026**. As of the date of this document, the publisher has not provided a formal response or updated the article's status.

Recommendation to Readers:

We strongly advise researchers and practitioners **NOT TO CITE** or rely on the findings of this article until a formal retraction or corrected version is processed by the journal.

4. Contact Information

For further clarification regarding this concern, please contact:

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